

A Comparative Study on Organizational Climate between Public and Private Organizations

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Abstract

The present study is intended to compare the organizational climate between the public organizations and the private organizations in Myanmar. The purposes are : (1) to assess the organizational climate of the organizations studied with regard to six types of motives, (2) to find out the differences in the organizational climate among the three public organizations, (3) to find out the differences in the organizational climate among the three private organizations, and (4) to compare the organizational climate between the public and the private organizations with regard to six types of motives. Three hypotheses were formulated. The first hypothesis was that there were differences in organizational climate among the three public organizations studies. The second hypothesis was that there were differences in organizational climate among the three private organizations studies. The third hypothesis was that there were differences in organizational climate between public and private organizations. Motivational Analysis of Organizational Climate (MAO-C) questionnaire was used to diagnose the organizational climate from the standpoint of motivations. The questionnaire employed twelve dimensions of organizational climate and the six motives: achievement, expert influence, extension, control, dependency, and affiliation. Total of 407 organizational members who are working at three public organizations: Department of Social Welfare (DSW), University of East Yangon (UEY), and Gems Museum (GM), and three private organizations; Merlin organization, Eden center, and Pan Yoma Co., Ltd. In assessing the organizational climate, the findings indicated that the organizational climate of Department of Social Welfare (DSW) and Gems Museum (GM) was dependency-achievement climate. The organizational climate of University of East Yangon (UEY) was dependency-expert influence climate. The findings indicated that organizational climate of Merlin was extension-dependency climate. The organizational climate of Eden was dependency-achievement climate. The organizational climate of Pan Yoma was dependency-expert influence climate. With regard to the three public organizations, the findings indicated that there were no significant differences in achievement, extension, and affiliation motive. And then, there were significant differences in expert influence motive, control motive, and dependency motive among the three public organizations. The findings also indicated that there were significant differences in achievement motive, extension motive, control motive, dependency motive and affiliation motive except expert influence motive among the three private organizations. The findings also pointed out that there were significant differences in achievement motive, extension motive, control motive, and dependency motive except expert influence and affiliation motive between the three public organizations and three private organizations.

Introduction

Our society is composed of many different kinds of organizations. These organizations affect our lives in important ways. The standard of living, health, well-being, education and security depend upon how effectively these organizations achieve their objectives. Behavioral scientists are concerned with studying the behavior of individuals and groups in organizations, as well as the organization in its entirety. It is hoped that these complex phenomena will be explained so as to enhance organization effectiveness and the satisfaction of members of the organization. In order to achieve this objective, they must address themselves to a wide spectrum of problems that arise in work organizations. In today's competitive business environment, organizations are always looking for ways to gain an advantage over their competitors.

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Successful organizations realize the value of creating a work environment (or climate) that is pleasant, and motivates employees to be committed and effective performers. Organizational climate, which depends on the perception of organizational members and significantly influences their motivation and behavior, is a conceptual synthesis of characteristics that distinguish organizations from one another. This research is intended to study and compare the organizational climate between public and private organizations in Myanmar. Formal organizations, such as business firms, hospitals, schools, prisons, labor unions, and government agencies, occupy a dominant position in today's highly specialized and technologically advanced society. Between organizations, climates differ in friendliness, seriousness, graciousness, orderliness, criticalness, and so on. For studying organizational climate, motivational framework seems to be quite relevant. The motivational framework of climate includes six motives: achievement, expert influence, control, extension, dependency and affiliation. These motives are relevant for understanding and examining the behavior of people in organizations.

The main objectives of this study are

- (1) to explore the motivational climate of the three public and three private organizations and
- (2) to compare the organizational climate between public and private sectors.

Method

Quantitative method and analysis of variance method will be used in this research. In the first phase, Motivational Analysis of Organizational Climate Questionnaire (MAO-C) (Udai Pareek, 1989) was adapted into Myanmar Culture. In the second phase, the differences in organizational climate (or) motivational climate of the organizational studied were computed by means of analysis of variance.

Participants

In this study, total of 407 organizational members who are working at three public and three private sectors were used as subjects. They were administered Motivational Analysis of Organizational Climate (MAO-C) questionnaire. Three public organizations were Department of Social Welfare(DSW), East Yangon University (EYU), and Gems Museum (GM). Three private organizations were Merlin, Eden, and Pan Yoma. Merlin organization provides services for primary health care and water and sanitation hygiene. Eden organization is the training center for disabled children. Pan Yoma company limited is the organization which manufactures the strings. There were 15 males and 52 females of DSW, 19 males and 73 females of EYU, and 21 males and 36 females of GM. For the three private organizations, 33 males and 27 females of Merlin, 28 males and 32 females of Eden and 47 males and 24 females of Pan Yoma organizations were included.

Materials

In this study Motivational Analysis of Organizational Climate (MAO-C) questionnaire was constructed based on organizational climate questionnaire of Udai Pareek (1989). MAO-C questionnaire was used to diagnose the organizational climate from the standpoint of motivations. The focus of the instrument can be perceptions of the overall organizational climate or of individual units, divisions, branches or departments within the organization. The questionnaire employed twelve dimensions of organizational climate and the six motives: achievement, expert influence, extension, control, dependency, and affiliation. MAO-C questionnaire consisted of twelve categories of organizational climate, each of which included six statements. Each of these categories corresponded to one of the twelve climate dimensions, each of the six statements responded one of the six motives. Items were adapted into organizational life of Myanmar culture. There were 72 items. Six experts in psychological measurement were asked to comment on any item that they found ambiguous or difficult to understand. Items were tried out with a sample of 37 organizational members. Some of them were

staff of Cooperative Bank and some of them were teaching staff in Taungoo area. These queries did not reveal any major changes and no modification needed to be made to any of the items.

Procedure

MAO-C consisted of twelve climate dimensions and six motives. Each of the six statements represented one of the six motives. The participants were given the questionnaire booklets and instructed them to answer all questions on the answer sheet and requested not to omit any items. In the answer sheet of MAO-C questionnaire, the participant's age, gender, department, role, name of organization, and date were presented. The participants were told that there were twelve categories in the MAO-C representing twelve dimensions of organizational climate; and they were asked to rank six statements in order of the participants' liking from 'most like' (the situations in their units) to "least like" (the situation in their units). "Most like" was given a score of 6 while the "least like" a score of 1. They were requested not to give the same rank to more than one statement. Administration time was approximately 20 minutes. The data analysis was done by descriptive statistics and parametric techniques. The parametric (t-test) also was used to compare the significant differences in organizational climate between three public sectors and three private sectors

Results and Discussion

After administering the questionnaire, the data were computed and the following results were obtained.

Table(1) Indexes of Motivational Analysis of Organizational Climate for three public organizations in terms of six types of motives or climates

Organizations	Indexes with regard to six types of motives						Dominant	Back-Up
	Achievement	Expert-Influence	Extension	Control	Dependency	Affiliation		
DSW	53.19	52.26	52.21	41.02	59.76	40.98	Dependency	Achievement
EYU	51.82	57.02	51.31	36.64	61.76	41.42	Dependency	Expert-Influence
GM	53.52	50.27	49.27	46.48	54.21	43.27	Dependency	Achievement

Table (1) showed the indexes of motivational analysis of organizational climate of three public organizations. According to the table (1), the dominant and back-up motives for three public organizations were shown respectively.

Table(2) Indexes of Motivational Analysis of Organizational Climate for three private organizations in terms of six types of motives or climates

Organizations	Indexes with regard to six types of motives						Dominant	Back-Up
	Achievement	Expert-Influence	Extension	Control	Dependency	Affiliation		
Merlin	37.04	54.39	66.04	42.84	60.18	38.12	Extension	Dependency
Eden	54.84	53.51	49.58	38.87	55.03	47.74	Dependency	Achievement
Pan Yoma	50.30	54.50	46.36	50.26	57.50	41.63	Dependency	Expert-Influence

Table (2) showed the indexes of motivational analysis of organizational climate of three private organizations. According to the table (2), the dominant and back-up motives for three private organizations were shown respectively.

Table(3) Differences between Public and Private Organizations with respect to six types of motivational climate

Motivational Climate	Types of Organizations	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig. level
Achievement	Public	216	43.39	6.62	4.490	0.01*
	Private	191	40.38	6.90		
Expert Influence	Public	216	44.70	7.07	0.442	0.66 NS
	Private	191	44.42	5.76		
Extension	Public	216	42.60	6.22	2.738	0.01*
	Private	191	44.44	7.32		
Control	Public	216	36.20	9.22	2.527	0.01*
	Private	191	38.34	7.63		
Dependency	Public	216	48.30	7.51	2.518	0.01*
	Private	191	46.55	6.83		
Affiliation	Public	216	36.81	8.41	1.282	0.20 NS
	Private	191	37.81	7.11		

*p<.01 significance level

Table (3) showed the differences between the three public and three private organizations concerning with the six types of motivational climates were analyzed by using a test of significant difference between two independent means (t-test). According to table(3), there were significant differences in achievement motive, extension motive, control motive, dependency motive at 0.01 levels.

Discussion

The findings in table (1) showed that the indexes of motivational analysis of organizational climate for three public organizations. According to the findings, the dominant motive was dependency and the back-up motive was achievement for the Department of Social Welfare (DSW). The organizational climate of the Department of Social Welfare was dependency-achievement climate. According to this climate, the members of DSW focused on the achievement and those in positions of power were emphasized. Freedom was granted to employees, but key decisions were controlled by those in power.

According to the findings shown in table (1), for East Yangon University, the dominant motive was dependency and the back-up motive was expert influence. The organizational climate of East Yangon University was dependency-expert influence climate. According to this climate, East Yangon University had a hierarchy and decisions were made by those at higher levels. Experts played an important role in the various aspects of organizational life.

For Gems Museum, according to the findings shown in table (1), the dominant motive was dependency and the back-up motive was achievement. The organizational climate of Gems Museum was dependency-achievement climate. Thus, the climate of Museum was similar to that of the Department of Social Welfare.

The findings in table (2) showed the indexes of motivational analysis of organizational climate for three private organizations. The dominant motive was extension and the back-up motive was dependency for Merlin organization. The organizational climate of Merlin was extension-dependency climate. With respect to this climate, the business of Merlin organization was community service. Emphasis was placed on conformity to the policies laid down by the top person or team, to whom all final decisions were referred.

For Eden organization, the dominant motive was dependency and the back-up motive was achievement. The organizational climate of Eden was dependency-achievement climate. Thus, the characteristics of this climate were similar to that of the Department of Social Welfare.

The dominant motive was dependency and the back-up motive was expert influence for Pan Yoma organization. The organizational climate of Pan Yoma was dependency-expert influence climate. Thus, the characteristics of this climate were similar to those of East Yangon University.

In this study, most of the organizations were influenced by dependency motive. This was due to Myanmar cultural settings. The dependency motive was characterized by a concern for approval and maintenance of hierarchical order. Regardless of public or private sectors, most of the members of Myanmar organizational settings seem to have a desire for the assistance of others in developing themselves and a need to check with those who are more knowledgeable or have higher status, experts, and close associates. They had also a tendency to submit ideas or proposals on the other person's approval. Only Merlin organization was influenced by the extension motive. The extension motive was characterized by a concern for relevance to larger goals and entities. Based on some of the studies that had been made, most of the community-service organizations were influenced by the extension motive. Since the business of Merlin organization was community service, it was influenced by the extension motive. In this organization, supervisor focused on helping their subordinates to improve personal skills and chances of advancement.

Differences between the three public and three private organizations concerning the six types of motivational climates were analyzed by using a test of significant difference between two independent means (t-test) and results were shown in table (3). The respondents in this study were 216 members of three public organizations and 191 members of three private organizations.

According to the findings shown in table (3), regarding with the achievement motivational climate, there was significant difference in achievement motivational climate between public and private organizations at 0.01 levels. The achievement motive was characterized by concern for excellence. In public organizations studied, employees were involved in a highly stimulated by challenging tasks. The members of public organizations worked on challenging goals and emphasized

high achievement. In other words, in private organizations, although the quality of work was emphasized, members of these private organizations did not appear to be differentiating from one another on the basis of achievement results.

With respect to the expert influence motivational climate, there was no significant difference in expert influence motivational climate between the public organizations and the private organizations at 0.66 levels. The expert influence motive was characterized by a concern for impact through expertise. It can be said that the members of both sectors were equally motivated for expert influence.

With regard to the extension motivational climate, there were significant differences in extension motive between the public organizations and the private organizations at 0.01 levels. The extension motive was characterized by a concern for relevance to larger goals and entities. Supervisory practices contributed significantly to climate and atmosphere. In private organizations, since supervisors focused on helping their subordinates to improve personal skills and chances of advancement, a climate that was characterized by the extension motive may result. In other words, the members of the public organizations did not appear to be differentiating from one another on the basis of the need to pay attention to the employees' needs and welfare.

With respect to the control motivational climate, there were significant differences in control motivational climate between the public organizations and the private organizations at 0.01 levels. The control motive was characterized by a concern for orderliness. In this study, the private organizations were run in accordance with detailed procedures, and had a clear hierarchy. In these organizations, decisions were usually delayed because actions were generally referred to higher levels for approval. It was more important to follow rules and regulations than to achieve results. On the other hand, the members of public organizations did not appear to be differentiating from one another on the basis of the control motives

In accordance with the findings shown in table (3), with respect to the dependency motivational climate, there were significant differences in dependency motivational climate between the public organizations and the private organizations at 0.01 levels. The dependency motive was characterized by a concern for approval and maintenance of hierarchical order. In the public organizations, in spite of an emphasis on high achievement, decisions were made only at the upper levels of the hierarchy. The members of these public organizations seem to have a desire for the assistance of others in developing themselves and an urge to maintain a relationship based on the other person's approval. On the contrary, the members of the private organizations did not appear to be differentiating from one another on the basis of a tendency to submit ideas or proposals or approval.

According to the findings shown in table (3), with regard to the affiliation motivational climate, there was no significant difference in affiliation motivational climate between the public organizations and the private organizations at 0.20 levels. This motive can be characterized by a concern for maintaining good relations. The findings showed that the members of both organizations were equally motivated in affiliation motive.

Conclusion

The focus of this study was perceptions of the overall organizational climate. Organizational climate is created from the perception of organizational members about organizational dimensions. Perception, being a cognitive process, is influenced by the personality, motivation, learning and experience of the individual. Therefore, it is expected that organizational climate is influenced by factors that influence perception. The achievement motive, the expert influence motive, and the extension were useful and functional. The control motive, the dependency motive, and the affiliation motive were dysfunctional for an organization. In this study, all of the organizations studied except Merlin organization were influenced by dependency motive. Only Merlin organization was influenced by extension motive. Therefore, Merlin organization seemed to be functional than other organizations.

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